

Indonesian Wedding Organizer's Ecosystem Business Mapping

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ABSTRACT: Business growth in the wedding industry has begun to grow and spread in Indonesia, seen from the variety of types of this industry, one of which is wedding organizer (WO). WO is an organizer with many networks involved in its business ecosystem. It can't stand alone without relations and interactions with its stakeholders (vendors) such as wedding decor, catering, entertainment, make-up artist, and others. In this research, a conducive network model in the industry can be optimized by mapping the WO business ecosystem to expand and create a complete and sustainable business. The method used is qualitative, with data collection through interviews, observations, and literature studies. James F. Moore's business ecosystem will be used in data analysis as a mapping reference for WO business network model. The results found that several networks were classified into three scopes of the business ecosystem. It considers the relationship of each stakeholder to the WO and vice versa. The relationship between stakeholders resulted in two-way and one-way relationships and activities. It was also found that stakeholders may decrease or increase over time the development of creativity, technology, references, and processions that will be carried out at the wedding. For relationships with the highest interaction urgency, they can continue to occupy their permanent positions in the WO business ecosystem. The form of the WO business ecosystem as a whole cannot be determined by a single model and will continue to evolve according to the procession.

KEYWORDS: Business, Ecosystem, Stakeholder, Wedding Organizer

INTRODUCTION

This wedding service grew into a business industry in the 1920s in the United States, then expanded to Europe and other countries, including Indonesia (Kompasiana.com). Based on observations, in Indonesia itself, the growth of the wedding service business is also spreading. Marked by the existence of various types of service options such as Event Organizer with a broader scope, not only dealing with weddings but also other events; Wedding Planner who manages the schedule starting from the pre-event to the concept of the wedding event that will be carried; Stylish Wedding which is almost similar to the Wedding Planner business concept; Wedding Gallery which is in charge of organizing several vendors and already has the products or equipment needed for the wedding; and Wedding Organizer (WO) which is explicitly dealing with wedding issues. The Wedding Organizer is an organizer in charge of managing and coordinating wedding events from the beginning to the end of the event, and it cannot stand alone because its function is only as a coordinator. Hence, it requires other partners (stakeholders) to make the wedding event successful. Partners here are in the form of service vendors needed by clients or prospective brides, such as; decoration, entertainment, catering, make-up artist, attire, venue, and others. It can be customized by wishes, needs, and budgets offered by the WO or the client's request to be more flexible in the process. This ecosystem has an essential role in WO's business sustainability. However, it is not entirely dependent on WO because they have products and services that can be offered to clients. Some can also get their clients without having to depend on other partners. The role of other partners is still quite significant considering that promotions are primarily through word of mouth and the connections that have been established.

The discussion about this WO becomes interesting, especially about its business field and the mapping of the business networks involved in it. Because this WO is a network business that cannot live without other business partners, thus creating a symbiosis in it and allowing dependency from one partner to another, not just the WO. This matter the author to do this research and try to map the business ecosystem in the wedding organizer to examine a conducive ecosystem model for the development of the wedding organizer business into a complete and sustainable industry.

Mapping the business ecosystem here will refer to James F. Moore's theory which groups business networks into three layers. The first is core activities in the deepest layer, then business actors who interact directly with the innermost layer, and in the outermost layer, the actors who directly or indirectly affect the sustainability of the business concerned. This paper is expected to create a

business picture in increasing effectiveness, managing risk, and breaking through innovations, also by studying the business ecosystem according to James F. Moore in planning for the future and reducing the risk implications of a business.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Wedding Organizer

According to Sumarsono in Bestari (2020), Wedding Organizer is a service agency that serves explicitly the bride and groom to prepare all the needs of the wedding event so that it runs smoothly as desired. Meanwhile, Rahman (2020) explained that the main challenge for WO services is consistency in getting new customers because ‘normally’ marriage will only be done once in a lifetime. That explains that choosing a business partner or network in a WO cannot be underestimated for the sake of business continuity and clients’ trust in service providers so that they get continuous attention, such as word-of-mouth promotions of clients who have used these services.

Business Ecosystem

The business ecosystem according to Townsend in Yusuf (2017), is a form of relationship between organizations or networks that is dynamic, interrelated, and interdependent to be able to continue the sustainability of a particular business.

Moore in Corallo et al. (2007) the business ecosystem as a network that works cooperatively to incorporate innovation among suppliers, distributors, and outsourcing companies to satisfy customer needs. The mapping of the business ecosystem is referenced by James F. Moore, who classified the network into three layers, while the stages in the classification of ecosystems are as follows:

1. Identify the role emphasized on the type or types of business actors in the ecosystem.
2. Role specifications include work, activities, and typical outputs from the previously identified types of roles and their relationship to other roles.
3. Describing ecosystems based on mapped roles provides space for other possible roles and interactions as intermediaries.
4. Create a narrative about the interaction between roles starting from customer activities in the ecosystem.

Analysis of the ecosystem created as an evaluation of the interactions that occur from each role, the resources needed for specific roles that allow for the existence of other actors, etc.

Figure 1. Business Ecosystem Actors by James F. Moore

METHODOLOGY

The research method is qualitative by collecting interview data from the parties involved in the wedding organizer (WO) business, such as; the owner of WO, music entertainment, invitation designer, and other vendors who cooperate with WO. There are also observations, looking into the field when a wedding is taking place, and literature studies which have also discussed a lot about the wedding organizer business. The classification and analysis stages will refer to the theory of James F. Moore, which has been described previously as the leading theory used in this research.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Data were collected through observation and interviews with several vendors involved in the WO business ecosystem. Data collection is done virtually online using a Zoom meeting or via Whatsapp call and chat during the March-May period. From the results of the interview, it was found that several vendors who can work with WO are as follows:

- 1. Wedding Organizer Team**

The team here consists of teams in the field and at the wedding organizer's office. Some are involved before the D-day of the event, and some are involved only on the D-day of the event. Some are involved from the start until the end of the marriage.
- 2. Wedding Décor**

Wedding decorations manage all equipment related to room decoration (indoor or outdoor), ranging from aisles, guest chairs, guest guards, VIP rooms for the bridal family, and so on. Decorations are usually done according to the request of the bridal couple or from the customer. Some of the wedding decoration themes that are often used include; traditional, modern national, rustic, thematic wedding (using certain unique themes), vintage, shabby chic, and so on.

The relationships are usually built with several vendors supplying decoration raw materials such as florists, boards, wood, paint, and others. In addition, for warehouse decoration vendors, work/assembly and storage of goods and other necessities are also needed. The workforce is the same, craftsmen are mobilized to assemble various kinds of decorations (on D-day or before), and these craftsmen can be employed in internal production or remunerate them to special craftsmen from certain areas or commonly referred to as custom decor.

Catering

Catering vendors are in charge of providing a banquet on the wedding day, usually there are several choices of food according to the wedding theme or custom used at the event. Caterers can work with suppliers of raw materials for food, be it markets, mini markets, supermarkets, and even individuals who handle food raw materials.
- 3. Master of Ceremony**

The Master Ceremony, commonly known as the MC, guides the event. The MC is given a rundown briefing from the WO to guide the event to be lively and run as it should.
- 4. Music Entertainment**

Music Entertainment can be in the form of a band, acoustic, single organ, or other music that can be performed at a wedding. MCs also often have special ties to entertainment vendors or WOs themselves. The network they build usually generates recommendations from each other to clients.

As a provider of entertainment services, there are usually two types of these services. The first is a player or in a group, such as a band and acoustic, where they can play musical instruments but do not have a sound system that is qualified for specific events. Usually, this type rents back tools they do not have so they can play or appear at weddings or other events. Then the second type is a provider of tools for music entertainment purposes. Apart from providing tools, they usually have their team as music players, or at least they have a network of cooperation with certain entertainment bands or music groups.
- 5. Custom/Tradition**

Adat is optional. Indonesian people usually use certain customs in their marriages to carry out hereditary culture and follow the beliefs believed in certain traditional processions. Customs can be in the form of cultural arts such as dance which is usually displayed when opening reception, for example, Manjapuik Marapulai in Minanese customs, Palang Pintu in Betawi customs, and other customs that are pretty diverse in each tribe and culture. Some customs are carried out at pre-wedding events, such as Siraman, Malam Bainai, Recitations, and others. Cooperation and relationships are usually done with make-up artists or traditional clothing/costumes providers.
- 6. Make-up Artist**

The make-up artist is in charge of doing make-up for the bride and groom and the bride's family (depending on the package taken), starting from applying make-up and helping to pair the bride's clothes and accessories, as well as the hairdo. Most make-up artists also provide wedding attire or vice versa. If not, they collaborate more because their work is interrelated. The clients they receive also get recommendations from one of them so that the bond between the make-up artist and the wedding attire cannot be separated because the job descriptions are in line with each other. Make-up artists independently have connections with certain salons. Besides that, they also have relationships with make-up tools and accessories suppliers

as a means of combat. In this modern era, make-up artists are required to be more agile and active so that potential consumers will trust them, and one way is to get certificates through seminars or workshop events to develop their skills of make-up artists.

7. Wedding Attire

Wedding attire provides clothes and accessories for the bride and groom, parents, several families (optional), bridesmaids, groomsmen, and others (by request). As previously explained, wedding attire is connected more often with make-up artists. In addition, this vendor will also cooperate with fashion designers for fashion design, as well as tailors for production execution. Suppliers of raw materials are also needed here, such as providers of fabrics and sequins—the craftsmen who can also be involved in the continuity of this business.

8. Documentation (Photography & Videography)

Photographers and videographers are in charge of handling documentation during the event and usually also handle pre-wedding photos, which are held one month before the event takes place to be printed and displayed on the D-day of the event. For photographers, collaboration with equipment and tool providers is sometimes needed due to a lack of inventory or just starting their business slowly. Photographers can also work with wedding invitation vendors for publication needs displayed on the relevant invitation surface. WO sometimes require pre-wedding photos to be printed and used as wedding decorations on D-day.

9. Venue

As the venue for the event, especially in hotel ballrooms, this venue usually provides catering packages at once. Not infrequently, clients have prepared their venue for the event, then consulted their event with the WO so that the WO does not need to find a place for the event and only needs to communicate further to cooperate with the venue the client has determined.

10. Henna Artist

Henna is usually an optional component used by the bride to decorate her hands and feet. In certain customs, henna is one of the cultures that are carried out before the wedding reception. For example, in Minangnese, there is what is called the *Malam Bainai* Tradition, as well as the Malay Culture, which calls it *Malam Berinai*, while in Buginese tradition is called the Traditional Ceremony *Mappacci*.

11. Bouquet

Taking care of the flowers that the bride will use. These flower craftsmen certainly need to supply fresh flowers or at least artificial flowers. They can work with farmers, the flower market, or indeed they can have their garden.

12. Wedding Invitation

The bride and groom certainly need an invitation to inform the guests so that they can be present as witnesses of their happiness on the day of the event. Some invitation vendors still depend on the printing house. In other words, the invitation vendors can complement each other and work together. Even though they can print their production, some tools they do not have for additional complements in the invitation design will be handed over to other printing vendors. For example, printing A receives a client, the basic design and printing process is carried out at A's production house, the client asks for the name font in the invitation using gold ink and embosses it. At the same time, Printing A does not yet have the tools for the request, so these stages are handed over to Printing B. In addition, invited vendors also often work with photographers, as previously explained.

13. Souvenir

Even though they have used the services of WO, clients also often look for souvenirs to be given to guests, so the collaboration between this vendor and WO is very flexible, depending on the client's request. The types of souvenirs are also increasingly diverse, and they can come from mass products and even artisans depending on the bride and groom's choice.

Ammunition above is vendors generally needed so that WO can stay alive. The new vendors who entered during the pandemic due to limited space for movement are as follows:

1. Digital Invitation

Because times have become more sophisticated and there are limitations to moving during a pandemic, the previously used printed invitations have now been replaced by digital invitations. This service makes it easier for the bride and groom to

convey information to their guests. Besides being more efficient because the costs incurred do not count the number of invitation sheets, the bride and groom will not be afraid to run out of invitations so that more guests can be invited/informed about their wedding. They are also convenient and more secure during a pandemic because the bride-to-be does not have to mobilize to deliver her invitations to the guests' homes.

Not much different from conventional invitations, digital invitations also often work with photographers but do not involve printing. They refer to the application or web system used to design and distribute client invitations.

2. Digital Guestbook

A digital guestbook functions like a typical guestbook but in an online form. Guests who cannot attend can fill in attendance in this guest book or confirm attendance if they can attend on D-day. Usually, this guest book is given along with the invitation, and guests can also send gifts in the form of digital money that can be transferred to several platforms and write congratulations and prayers to the bride and groom.

3. Live streaming

Live streaming is used for invitees who cannot attend the event or are invited to attend only via virtual because of the limited number of guests who can attend the reception. The live stream will usually be connected via the Youtube platform, the Zoom application, or other applications.

Vendors with incomplete equipment such as cameras, external mics, spare batteries, and others. Usually, renting these tools to photo and video equipment providers, so they need cooperation between live streaming vendors and the provision of rental tools for photo and video needs.

In addition, some actors are not directly related to the core business and even extended enterprises but have a significant influence on the sustainability of the wedding organizer business, namely as follows:

1. Social Media Interaction

Social media is very needed in building the branding of a business; when a WO is seen as good, the level of public trust in a WO can be obtained so it can increase sales of WO services themselves and are better known with a broader scope. Lately, many audiences have favored social media, are Instagram, Tiktok, Facebook, and YouTube, which are also reasons for business people to use these platforms.

2. Wedding Organizer Association

As a forum for sharing information about the wedding industry and unifying business people in this industry, some of which are:

HASTANA (Association of Wedding Organizers) is an organization that has the vision to bring together wedding planning companies, wedding organizers, and wedding planners in Indonesia—building brotherly relationships and getting to know each other to create a collaboration. That makes HASTANA a professional organization in the field of wedding stylists so that it can become a primary reference in stakeholders.

ASPEDI (Association of Indonesian Decoration Service Entrepreneurs), unlike before, ASPEDI as an association with a scope that focuses on decoration services. There are already more than a thousand members from ASPEDI from all over Indonesia with a function that is not much different from before, namely as a sharing forum and professional organization focusing on decoration services.

3. Office of Religious Affairs (KUA)

Although not directly communicating with the WO, KUA plays a significant role in the continuity of the marriage of the two prospective brides. One of the activities that can be built between WO and KUA is scheduling events, but this can be done through intermediaries of the bride and groom.

4. Places of Worship

Places of worship can be a place for weddings to take place, WO is also not directly related to the person in charge of the place of worship. Usually, it has been determined directly by the committee from the nuclear family of the prospective bride and groom.

5. Hotel/lodging

The hotel can also be an event venue. With its position within scope 3, the hotel is a place to stay for some guests, especially the extended family of the bride and groom, so the relationship with the WO occurs indirectly.

The following is the result of mapping the Wedding Organizer Ecosystem based on the scope of interaction according to James F. Moore, which is classified into three scopes, as follows:

- a. Scope 1 – Core Business, mapping the core activities in a business. The networks included in scope 1 in the WO business mapping with a higher level of urgency are as follows; wedding décor, make-up artist, wedding attire, photographer, venue, catering, and entertainment. Meanwhile, other core businesses that have less urgency are wedding invitations, custom traditions, henna artists, master of ceremony (MC), bouquets, souvenirs, digital invitations, digital guest books, and live streaming. Considerations in the grouping of core business are based on the urgency level. Figure 2 shows the core business in the dotted circle as a WO relationship which is considered very urgent because the primary need in a wedding procession is in the network within the circle. In contrast, as previously mentioned, the network outside the circle has a low level of urgency for a relationship with WO because not all WO will relate directly to these vendors. Usually, clients will contact each of them directly so that WO receives a list of vendors outside that they have prepared beforehand. The next consideration is because the core business outside the dotted circle is an optional part of a procession; for example, traditional custom vendors will not be used when the event procession does not use the traditional concept. In addition, the consideration is because the communication between the WO and the vendors is caused by the client or, in other words, as an extension.
- b. Scope 2 – Extended Enterprise, direct interaction by business actors in core business activities. In scope 2, the author again describes WO partners collaborating with other partners to fulfill their needs, such as raw material suppliers, separate customers, and others. Scope 2 becomes a sub-network where they are needed but are not directly connected to the WO but are related to the network or vendors in the core business. Here are some extended enterprises in the WO business ecosystem; In terms of needs, there are suppliers of raw materials who can relate to several vendors. Such as decoration vendors who need to supply florists, wood, boards, and building materials, as well as catering vendors who require raw food materials for cooking. Then there are human resources that each vendor needs, at least as a core team or crew on duty from the vendor. Some craftsmen are needed for decorating decorations, flower arrangements, custom equipment, and others. Lastly, cooperation with vendors produces relationships, recommendations to clients, and two-way relationships needed during event processions, for example, between make-up artists and wedding attire.

The following table describes the relationship between the core business and the extended enterprise.

Table 1. Extended Enterprise Grouping by Activity and Relationship

CORE BUSINESS	EXTENDED ENTERPRISE		
	Supplier	Human Resource	Relationships between Vendors
Wedding decor	Flowers, wood, boards, building shops, and others.	Office team, Field PIC, craftsmen, builders, and others.	Documentation
Catering	Food ingredients supplier (supermarkets, minimarkets, resellers, etc.)	Chef, helper, admin, and others.	Hotel (also as wedding venue)
MC	Attire	Team/individual as MC	Entertainment
Music Entertainment	Musical instruments, sound system	Music player, vocalist, band, nasyid, sound engineer, sound man, etc.	MC, traditional customs
Custom Tradition	Traditional musical instruments/instruments, traditional equipment (costumes, make-up, etc.), traditional equipment (for events such as <i>siraman</i> , etc.) and so on.	Players, dancers, office teams, field teams, etc. (adjusted to the traditional procession held)	MC, make-up artist, attire/traditional costume provider.
Make-up Artist	Make-up tools, accessories, salons, and so on.	Admin, make-up team	Wedding attire, documentation
Wedding Attire	Raw materials (fabric, sequins, yarn, sewing tools, etc.), fabric shops, sewing equipment shops, and so on.	admin/office team, fashion designer, fashion stylist, tailor, sequin craftsman, and others.	Make-up artist, documentation

Documentation	Documentation equipment and tools	Office/admin team, photographer team, videographer team, editor, and others.	Make-up artist, wedding attire, wedding invitation
Venue	-	Office/admin team	Catering, traditional custom
Bouquette	Artificial flowers, fresh flowers, flower markets, gardens, and more	Craftsmen, farmers, etc.	Wedding décor, wedding attire
Wedding Invitation	Printing	Office team, craftsmen, graphic designer, etc.	Photographer, digital wedding invitation
Digital Wedding Invitation	Website, e-wallet	Office team, graphic designer, UI designer/web designer, developer, etc.	Documentation, wedding invitation
Live streaming	Video equipment provider	Office team, field team, editor, designer etc.	Documentation, wedding invitation

The grouping of extended enterprises is made to make it easier to understand based on the activities, needs, and actors involved in the core business, the highest level of urgency is found in suppliers. In reality, suppliers here can continue to grow following the procession carried out at weddings, as well as human resources and vendors are related in a two-way relationship. Options will follow the needs of the ongoing procession.

- c. Scope 3 – Business Ecosystem, mapping business actors who can affect business continuity, either directly or indirectly. In this scope, many organizations, businesses, and even individuals can enter the WO business ecosystem. However, the author sets out several partners who are related indirectly but have the highest urgency, such as; social media interaction, KUA, places of worship, lodging (hotels), and WO business associations. Later in its development, partners in scope three can also increase or decrease according to the procession.

Figure 2. Wedding Organizer Business Ecosystem Mapping Model based on Diagram of Business Ecosystem Actors James F. Moore

Based on diagram Figure. 2, the direct relationship between the WO team and the leading vendors: wedding décor, make-up artist, wedding attire, documentation, venue, catering, and music entertainment. That also makes the interaction in it an interaction that needs to be built urgently from the WO side to continue to survive in its business. Meanwhile, a direct relationship that does not produce an urgent interaction can be seen between the WO and the vendor; digital and printed invitations, custom, MC, henna artist, bouquets, souvenirs, digital guest books, and live streaming, which are very optional.

The second layer of the diagram is the urgent interaction of an ecosystem with the resources it needs. There is also a relationship between vendors that do not result in urgent interactions, which can change according to circumstances, needs, and the environment in the business.

While the outermost layer, or the third layer, is a non-urgent relationship from the WO side but influences business continuity, either directly or indirectly, which can continue to grow as the business continues.

From these results, it can be concluded that the wedding organizer business can work with many vendors and will continue to grow following the wishes and needs of the client, the WO itself, and even the surrounding conditions.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

By examining the wedding organizer ecosystem model in this article, it is found that a WO industry generally cannot stand alone without the surrounding network. This network can change, increase, or even decrease. This adjustment is made for a sustainable business based on the client's needs and capabilities, the ability of the WO business itself, and the process to be carried out. In the course of the WO business, from year to year, it will experience changes or will not be the same as in previous years. The increasing number of references, environmental changes, technological sophistication, to human creativity in organizing an event can also turn the wheel in this business trend or at least add relationships and activities that can be done. Overall, the form of the wedding organizer business ecosystem cannot be determined by just one model. However, permanent relationships (relations that are considered the most urgent) will always be in place from time to time. Positions for other networks can be disassembled according to the needs and developments of the environment and the process so that this is a complete and sustainable industrial form of a wedding organizer business.

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